

ISic0210

I.Sicily inscription 0210

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [D(is)] M(anibus)

2. [---][P]rimo

3. [---][f]rat,ę[r]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285279

EDR 127500

EDCS 10900658

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a

l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0782

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 133

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0210. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334594>